

Design and Development of Itraconazole Bioadhesive Microspheres for Management of Fungal Infection

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Abstract: Sustained drug delivery has been the primary focus of pharmaceutical research in recent decades. The issue of barriers has been addressed via many methods, such as exploring new methods of administering substances. The Pharmaceutical Scientists are effectively facing the challenge of harnessing drug molecules for safer, more effective, and enhanced therapies in the rapidly changing and highly demanding field of healthcare. The innovative medication delivery system aims to improve the safety and effectiveness of therapeutic molecules by developing a user-friendly dose form for administration and ensuring greater patient adherence. Mucoadhesive microspheres containing itraconazole were used to improve the bioavailability of the medicine at the oral buccal location for the treatment of oral candidiasis. The formulation IMM5, which consists of mucoadhesive microspheres carrying itraconazole, is considered the most optimal formulation due to its incorporation of a naturally occurring polysaccharide polymeric mix in the drug composition. Guar gum is a substance that consists of a mixture of Xanthan gum in a ratio of 1:1:1. This mixture has the ability to release over 98.13% of a medicine in the stomach, in a controlled and sustained way for up to 12 hours.

Introduction: Medication delivery systems (DDS) with the ability to accurately regulate the rate of medication release or direct pharmaceuticals to a particular location in the body have had a significant influence on the healthcare system. Over the last twenty years, there has been a cutting-edge collaboration between the polymer and material science sectors in the pharmaceutical business, leading to the creation of innovative drug delivery methods. Carrier technology provides a smart method for delivering drugs by attaching them to carrier particles like microspheres, nanoparticles, liposomes, etc. This helps control the release and absorption

properties of the medicine. Microspheres play a significant role in these particulate drug delivery systems due to their tiny size and effective carrier properties [1]. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of these innovative drug delivery systems is restricted by their brief duration of stay at the absorption site. Therefore, it would be beneficial to have a method for establishing close contact between the DDS and the absorbent membranes. The achievement may be accomplished by combining the bioadhesion properties with microspheres and creating innovative delivery methods known as "bioadhesive microspheres". Bioadhesion may be defined as the process of attaching a synthetic or biological macromolecule to a biological tissue. An adhesive relationship may develop with either the epithelial cell layer, the continuous mucus layer, or both simultaneously [2]. The word "bioadhesion" refers to the bonding between a mucous covering and an adhesive polymeric device, while "cytoadhesion" refers to the particular attachment of cells. The process of bioadhesion has been thoroughly examined. The analysis of adhesion between mucin and mucoadhesive polymers often involves examining the molecular forces of attraction and repulsion. Bioadhesive microspheres include microparticles and microcapsules, ranging from 1 to 1000 μ m in diameter. These structures are composed either totally of a bioadhesive polymer or have an outside coating made of it, with the microcapsules containing a drug core. Microspheres have the potential to be used for targeted and controlled release drug delivery [3]. However, when bioadhesive properties are added to microspheres, there are additional advantages. These include efficient absorption and enhanced bioavailability of drugs due to a high surface to volume ratio, closer contact with the mucus layer, and the ability to specifically target drugs to the absorption site by attaching plant lectins, bacterial adhesins, antibodies, and other substances to the surface of the microspheres. Bioadhesive microspheres may be customized to stick to various mucosal tissues, such as those in the eye, nasal cavity, urinary tract, and gastrointestinal tract. This allows for the potential of targeted and controlled release of medications, both locally and systemically [4]. The application of bioadhesive microspheres to the mucosal tissues of the ocular cavity, stomach epithelium, and colonic epithelium is used for the localized delivery of medicines. Candidiasis is a common and substantial cause of oral irritation, pain, taste loss, and food aversion. Carrying *Candida albicans* and having a previous occurrence of candidiasis are other notable variables that increase the likelihood of developing oral candidiasis. Candidiasis is caused by the fungus *Candida albicans*, which usually exists in a harmless condition in the mouths of roughly half of healthy people [5]. Candidiasis is a prevalent illness in the mouth and surrounding areas caused by the excessive development of *Candida* fungi that naturally occur in the body. Maintaining excellent oral hygiene is crucial in preventing the recurrence of candidiasis in vulnerable patients aged [6-7].

This includes brushing and flossing the teeth twice a day and ensuring sufficient moisture in the mouth. Itraconazole is a white or almost white substance that is not easily dissolved in water, only slightly soluble in alcohol, easily dissolved in dichloromethane, and only somewhat soluble in tetrahydrofuran. The proposed experiment aims to build and analyze mucoadhesive microspheres of itraconazole for absorption in the oral buccal cavity. These microspheres will allow the drug to be absorbed directly from the mouth cavity. The current study postulated that the medicine was administered via the buccal route, resulting in a rapid beginning of action and improved bioavailability. The buccal mucosa has several benefits for sustained medication administration over long durations. The mucosa is abundantly equipped with both vascular and lymphatic drainage.

Material And Methods

Preparation of mucoadhesive Microspheres: Itraconazole bioadhesive microspheres were fabricated using the solvent evaporation technique. The Guar gum was dispersed in ethanol using a magnetic stirrer. Then, a suitable amount of the medicine Itraconazole and the polymer xanthan gum powder were added to the previously dissolved polymeric solution combination while stirring. The mixture was blended for 24 hours. Next, the suspension was gradually mixed with 250 ml of light liquid paraffin with a concentration of 1% tween 80, while stirring at a rate of 500 rpm. Following a 30-minute emulsification process, the solvents were progressively evaporated using a water-circulating vacuum pump until the microspheres were created. The microspheres underwent a washing process using petroleum ether and were then dried under vacuum conditions at room temperature [8].

Characterization of bioadhesive microspheres:

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) analysis: The morphology and surface characteristics of microspheres were examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) manufactured by Philips XL30 in the Netherlands. The microspheres were immersed in distilled water and the resulting mixture was applied onto a glass slide and allowed to dry under normal atmospheric conditions. The specimens were coated with a layer of gold in order to facilitate observation using scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

Particle size: Particle size was evaluated using the optical microscopy approach using a calibrated ocular lens.

Drug Encapsulation Efficiency: The entrapment efficiency was measured by removing the drug that was attached to the surface. The medication that was attached to the surface was eliminated by precisely adding a measured quantity of microspheres to 10 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer for a duration of 10 minutes, while shaking occasionally. The suspension was subjected to centrifugation at a speed of 3000 revolutions per minute for a duration of 5 minutes, resulting in the separation of the supernatant which was then set aside. The microspheres that had settled were treated again in the same way. The liquid that separated after centrifugation was combined with the initial liquid, and the concentration of the medication was evaluated using UV spectrophotometry at a wavelength of 265 nm.

Swelling Degree: Microspheres with known weight were placed in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer and allowed to swell until reaching a stable weight. The degree of weight increase was determined using the equation

$$DS = (W_{mf} - W_{mi}) / W_{mi},$$

where DS represents the degree of swelling, W_{mi} is the beginning weight of the microspheres, and W_{mf} is the final weight of the microspheres.

in-vitro bioadhesion: in-vitro bioadhesion investigations were conducted utilizing the Falling film method. The rat's intestinal mucosa was recently removed and placed on a tilted glass slide at a 45° angle. It was then cleaned with phosphate buffer saline for 30 minutes at a flow rate of 30 ml/min. A quantity of 100 mg of desiccated microspheres was scattered into the mucosal tissue and allowed to remain for a duration of 20 minutes to facilitate interaction. Throughout this duration, the whole system was put within a humidity chamber that was set to a relative humidity (RH) of 90%. The system was rinsed for 5 minutes at a flow rate of 22 milliliters per minute at the conclusion of the session. After the completion of this procedure, the separated particles were gathered and measured in terms of weight. The percentage of mucoadhesion was determined by using equation [9].

$$\% \text{ Bioadhesion} = \frac{\text{Wt of sample} - \text{Wt of detached particles} * 100}{\text{Wt of Sample}}$$

in-vitro drug release: A drug release investigation was conducted utilizing a modified USP dissolving test equipment, with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer serving as the medium. Microspheres containing medication were suspended in dissolving medium at a temperature of $37\pm 0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Periodically, samples were extracted and replaced with an equivalent volume of new dissolving medium. The drug content of the samples was evaluated by measuring absorbance at 265 nm using a UV spectrophotometer.

Results and Analysis: The current study focuses on the production of microspheres using the solvent evaporation method. These microspheres were successfully created with the desired characteristics. Additionally, the study explores the potential of using the buccal mucosa as a site for controlled delivery of macromolecular therapeutic agents, such as peptides, proteins, and polysaccharides. This is due to the accessibility and lower enzymatic activity of the buccal mucosa compared to the gastrointestinal tract. The SEM photos revealed that the particles of alginate/gelatin BBH loaded microspheres with significant elevation on their surfaces were mostly spherical in shape. Upon application of guar gum/ xanthan gum coating, the microcapsules exhibited a nearly spherical shape with slight elevations on their surfaces (Figure 1). The morphological characteristics seen may result from the sublimation of ice crystals during the lyophilization process, resulting in a porous and spongy surface. This might guarantee the presence of microspheres that possess excellent mobility and a significant specific surface area, resulting in enhanced medication absorption. Drug Entrapment The efficiency of the generated mucoadhesive microspheres was evaluated to determine the drug entrapment efficiency. The results ranged from 91.01% to 95.16%. The degree of swelling of microspheres, as well as the swelling rate and percent bioadhesion of mucoadhesive microspheres containing itraconazole, ranged from 62.5% to 79.9%. In-vitro dissolution studies serve as a means of quality control to ensure consistent product quality. These studies may be used to evaluate the effectiveness of sustained release formulations. The drug release from the microspheres was assessed in a phosphate buffer with a pH of 6.8. The results showed that microspheres prepared with a low drug to polymer ratio and high stirring speed in the simulated stomach fluid resulted in smaller microspheres. These smaller microspheres had a larger surface area, leading to a faster release of the medication. The first release of the medicine may occur from the substance that is not

encapsulated. The sluggishness of the second stage of the release process may be ascribed to the diffusion process of the enclosed medication from the microspheres. The scanning electron microscopic observation revealed the presence of guar gum polymer based microspheres, which exhibited surface non-uniformity. The BMI5 formulation, which consists of mucoadhesive microspheres containing itraconazole, is considered the most effective formulation. It is composed of a blend of naturally occurring polysaccharides, specifically guar gum and xanthan gum, in a ratio of 1:1:1. This formulation is capable of releasing over 99.13% of the drug in a controlled and sustained manner for up to 12 hours in the gastric environment. The drug release investigations were conducted in simulated gastrointestinal fluids with a pH of 6.8 phosphate buffer. The results of these studies were documented and may be seen in Table 2. Microspheres with buccal bioadhesive properties BMI5 is a superior formulation that consists of a naturally occurring combination of polysaccharide polymers, namely guar gum and xanthan gum in a 1:1:1 ratio. This formulation has the ability to release over 98.13% of the medicine in the stomach, in a controlled and sustained way for up to 12 hours. Regression analysis was conducted and the r^2 values indicated that the curves had a relatively linear relationship. Additionally, the slope values were calculated based on the graph. All batches had a release exponent "n" value greater than 0.89, confirming the presence of Super-case II transport mechanism (Figure 1). Regression analysis was conducted, and the r^2 values indicated that the curves had a relatively linear relationship. Additionally, the slope values were calculated based on the graph. All batches had a release exponent "n" value greater than 0.89, confirming the presence of the Super-case II transport mechanism.

Summary and Conclusion: Candidiasis is a common and treatable infection of the lining of the mouth that is often seen in patients with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection or acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS). Oral candidiasis may result in frequent and significant discomfort, pain, loss of taste, and aversion to eating. Being a carrier of *Candida albicans* and having a previous occurrence of oral candidiasis are significant additional risk factors for acquiring oral candidiasis. Candidiasis is a result of the presence of *candida albicans*, a kind of fungus that may occur in two distinct forms. Typically, this fungus is present in the oral cavities of around 50% of individuals who are in good health, without generating any negative effects. Buccal medication

delivery provides a beneficial alternative to oral drug administration, particularly in overcoming the constraints inherent with the latter approach to dose. Moreover, it is possible to provide medicine to those who are unable of oral intake by this approach. An optimal buccal drug delivery system should possess flexibility and exhibit robust bioadhesive properties, enabling it to effectively adhere to the oral cavity for the desired duration. Moreover, it is crucial that the medication be administered in a controlled and predictable manner to achieve the intended therapeutic outcome.

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Table 1: Various combinations of BMI1 – BMI5 based bioadhesive microspheres.

S. No.	Code	Ingredients	Drug : Polymer	Qty (mg)	Organic Solvent System	Stabilizing agent (PVA) (% w/v)
1	BMI1	Drug : Guragum	01:01	150:150	Ethanol	1
2	BMI2	Drug : Guragum	01:02	100:200	Ethanol	1
3	BMI3	Drug : Xanthan gum	01:01	150:150	Ethanol	1
4	BMI4	Drug : Xanthan gum	01:02	100:200	Ethanol	1
5	BMI5	Drug : Guragum: Xanthan gum	01:01:01	100:100:100	Ethanol	1

Table 2: Physical properties of mucoadhesive microsphere of itraconazole (BMI1 – BMI5)

S. No.	F. Code	davg (μm)	Drug content	Encapsulation efficiency (%)	Swelling rate (%)	Percent Bioadhesion
1	BMI1	351.15 $\pm$ 0.20	398.1	91.12	62.5 $\pm$ 1.11	85.63 $\pm$ 0.18
2	BMI2	382.06 $\pm$ 0.16	322.6	91.01	64.1 $\pm$ 1.04	87.11 $\pm$ 0.17
3	BMI3	393.17 $\pm$ 0.35	381.6	92.04	71.4 $\pm$ 0.18	91.02 $\pm$ 0.13
4	BMI4	387.23 $\pm$ 0.12	311.3	94.11	74.3 $\pm$ 1.11	94.11 $\pm$ 0.18
5	BMI5	396.24 $\pm$ 0.26	387.2	95.16	79.2 $\pm$ 114	95.11 $\pm$ 0.18

Figure 1: SEM analysis of porous bioadhesive microspheres

Figure 2: Zero-order kinetic dissolution data of mucoadhesive microsphere of itraconazole (BMI1 - BMI5)